

PRESENTATION OF PROCRAFT

PROtection & Conservation
of Heritage airCRAFT

I. Presentation of the project

1. Context of the project

World War II is often considered as being the golden age of military aviation, but aerial combat has left behind a large amount of wreckage in Europe, both on land and in the sea. This massive military engagement led to considerable both human and material loss.

Although **World War II aeronautical heritage** is undoubtedly of great historical and emotional value to Europeans, only recently have these remains officially entered the field of archaeology and cultural heritage conservation. They are not widely found in national museums and are often cared for by a range of volunteers and associations.

The **discovery of an aircraft wreck** presents a challenge from several points of view:

- its composition and materials,
- its history,
- its legal status,
- its size and condition.

Having been consulted several times regarding the conservation of aircraft wrecks, the **Arc'Antique laboratory** initiated a research project in 2013 on the conservation of aluminium alloys, in view of the limited knowledge on this type of cultural heritage. This project calls for the collaboration of other **national and international experts** who have been brought together within the framework of the European JPI-CH "PROCRAFT" project.

2. Objectives and expected results

Objectives:

This project aims to address the range of challenges related to the **conservation of aircraft wrecks** by connecting multiple players in the operational chain, from excavation to exhibition.

Our objectives are to create **innovative procedures and solutions** for each key step in aircraft conservation:

- tailored **conservation-restoration** techniques,
- innovative coatings for exterior **protection** respecting relevant criteria for the safeguard of cultural heritage,
- new solutions for **preventive** conservation in confined or semi-confined environments,
- **guidelines** for the restoration and conservation of Aluminium alloys for non-professionals.

Expected results:

The results of the project are expected:

- to improve and share **knowledge** about World War II aircraft
- to contribute to **preservation** by focusing particularly on the conservation of aluminium alloy (Al) components,
- to promote the **dissemination and presentation** of the project to the **public**,
- to strengthen **collaborative bonds** with our national and international partners.

3. Scope of the project

This European project is coordinated by the Arc'Antique laboratory. Scientists and associate partners (museums, associations, conservator-restorers, state representatives, mediators) from Italy, the Czech Republic and France representing all players in the heritage chain, will work together to share and mutually benefit from their respective skills and capacities over the 3-year period of the project (see Annex 1 for the list of main and secondary partners).

4. Beneficiaries of the project

There are multiple beneficiaries of this project:

- First, the **5 main contributors** to the project (Arc'Antique (GPLA, Nantes), the CEMES laboratory (CNRS, Toulouse), the Universities of Bologna (UNIBO) and Ferrara (UNIFE) (Italy) and the Technical University of Prague (CTU) (Czech Republic), who will have the opportunity to enhance their skills and expertise in the conservation of this type cultural heritage,
- Second, the **19 secondary contributors** to the project (referred to as associate partners in the European JPI-CH project), which include state structures responsible for managing this type of heritage (DRAC, DRASSM), museums and associations involved in its conservation, and restoration-conservation professionals,
- And finally, the **general public** who will be able to access this heritage thanks to the improved conservation of wrecks.

5. Citizen participation in the project

Our citizens are particularly interested in the 1939-1945 period for a number of reasons:

- the role of the remnants of war in the **(re)construction of memory**,
- the **familiar**, and even family, aspects of this historical period, because everyone has members of their family tree who lived through these **“dark days”**,
- the local and global impact of the war on **individual and national identity**.

The participation of ordinary citizens, as both active participants and beneficiaries, is therefore an essential component of this project.

Local or national associations responsible for aeronautical heritage are included as associate partners. They collaborate in the construction of research issues and benefit from the results. They will participate in the dissemination of results to be published in the annual newsletter aimed at the **general public**.

University and junior high-school students are also included in the project with:

- the organisation of at least one seminar for Archaeology students,
- a cultural education project for junior high-school students in association with local authorities
- the creation of a travelling exhibition in the form of information panels on World War II aircraft wrecks in several languages (English, French, Italian and Czech) to be used by all stakeholders.

6. Opportunities

In view of the growing demand for the study and preservation of this new form of heritage and the strong public interest in this period of history, this project is emerging in a favourable context. It incorporates the themes developed by the European call for projects (JPI-CH Conservation, Protection and Use Call) which selected it for funding by the ANR (National Research Agency).

This selection raises the national and international profile of the Arc'Antique laboratory as a major player in applied research and the conservation-restoration of archaeological collections.

7. Requirements of the project

As this project is in response to a European tender, it must respect the relevant requirements of European programmes, namely: to respect the provisional schedule, respect the provisional budget, respect European standards (conventional agreement), respect the programmed missions and tasks and how they are shared between the various contributors.

A series of **conventions** between partners must be signed:

- The consortium agreement between the main partners,
- Bilateral conventions between the main partners and their secondary partners.

These conventions are intended to guarantee the intellectual property of results as well as their use and to contractualise the commitment of active participants in the project.

The project **budget** will be subject to analytical monitoring in order to be able to provide the ANR with full information on expenditure monitoring for up to 5 years after the closure of the project (2028).

The completion of tasks and deliverables is based on a **project contract and paid internships** funded by the ANR grant. Particular attention must be paid to the implementation of these recruitments in accordance with the HR calendar and in the perspective of the project implementation schedule.

8. Key factors of success

As this project responds to a European tender, all the stages of the project have been detailed in the **call for projects file**: schedule, budget, missions, description and distribution of tasks between contributors (this file in English is available for consultation).

This groundwork has enabled us to lay down the framework for the implementation, monitoring and assessment of actions. The keys to success are:

- a work schedule and tasks clearly assigned to each player in the project,
- the description of expected deliverables validated by all partners,
- the strong commitment of each of the contributors in line with the administrative framework of the partnership agreements,
- Arc'Antique Laboratory's recognised and anticipated role as project coordinator,
- the existence of a dedicated budget

The project has been assessed by European experts who judged the **proposal as excellent**, awarding it a score of 14/15 and underlining that it includes all the necessary criteria to **be successful**. (<http://jpi-ch.eu/2020/02/conservation-protection-and-use-joint-call-results-available/>).